

THEME OF DISINTEGRATION IN AFGHANS IN THE LIGHT OF KHALED HOSSEINI'S NOVEL "A THOUSAND SPLENDID SUNS"

Majid Ali Khan¹, Hakim Ullah², Hajar Kamal³, Said Badshah⁴, Muhammad Anwar⁵, Murad Ali⁶, Hammad Hussain⁷

¹Lecturer, Department of English, University of Shangla

²BS Student, University of Shangla

⁷Department of English, University of Shangla

^{3,4,5,6}BS Student, Department of English, University of Shangla

¹majidalikhan@ushangla.edu.pk, ²hakimullah9593@gmail.com, ³hajarkamal337@gmail.com,

⁴saidbadshah2536@gmail.com, ⁵israrshangla36@gmail.com, ⁶mkihrar66723@gmail.com,

⁷hammadshangla33@gmail.com

¹ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0008-9675-4611>

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18410868>

Keywords

Afghan, Society, Foreign interventions, Rivalries, Conflicts

Article History

Received: 04 December 2025

Accepted: 14 January 2026

Published: 29 January 2026

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Murad Ali

Abstract

The aims of the present study at finding reasons behind the broken Afghan society while analyzing Afghan social and political life discussed in Khalid Hosseini's novel, "A Thousand Splendid Suns". It further highlights the negative role of different governments in the twentieth century and rivalries based on ethnicities and clans which helped deteriorate the condition of Afghan society. Moreover, it highlights the role of foreign interventions which have been facilitated by pre-existing conflicts of Afghan society. Besides, a thorough research has been carried out on the harmful effects on the Afghan people caused by wars and conflicts.

INTRODUCTION

A work of literature usually aims to portray what is hidden from the eyes of an average person. Literary writing is mainly inspired by what the writer sees and observes in his real life. Thus we can say that reality is the main aspect which literature tends to cover. The fundamental intention behind every great work of literature is to highlight the problem of contemporary society and to provide an ultimate solution to that problem.

For most of the modern literary writer "Literature is news that stays news" (Pound 29) which makes it clear that the sole purpose of literature in the

modern age is to provide an overview of a society and to enlighten the mind of an individual living in that society. Besides that, another main feature of literature according to Ezra Pound is its newness and its ability to attract the attention of the individuals from all sorts of societies. Moreover, a literary work usually has a long lasting effect on the mind of the readers. Briefly, we can say that not only entertainment, the basic purpose of a literary work is to address the problems of a society in the best possible way. And for this very reason Literature is considered as a mirror of

society. Writers such as Chaucer, Charles Dickens,

G. B. Shaw and William Golding always take a crack to present the actual portrait of what is happening in their surroundings. Art for the sake of humanity is the modern day trend crafted in the 20th century. Modern day artist starts believing that literature can play pivotal role in the reformation of society. Most of the modern day artist worked mainly for the development of society. Charles White, A modern African American artist, strongly believes that art can cooperate in the reformation of society. In one of his interviews he wished that he would do each and every thing in order to serve the purpose of social reform. The best possible function of a literary work is to imitate its surrounding. Great literary writers are considered as great because they aim to focus things which are mainly related to their society.

Literature in general is divided into Fiction and Non-Fiction. According to Oxford dictionary "Fiction is a form of literature which is written in prose, especially novels, which portray imaginary events and people:" Non-Fiction on the other hand is related to books, articles or text telling about real fact, life and peoples (Oxford Dictionary.)

Most of us usually confuse the term novel with short stories. According to the Oxford dictionary, Novel is "a fictitious prose narrative of book length, typically representing characters and action with some degree of realism:" while defines short story as "a story with a fully developed theme but significantly shorter and less elaborate than a novel. (Oxford Dictionary)" Thus, length differentiates the two genres. Writers like Katharine Mansfield, E. M. Foster and William Golding through their writing highlighted the miseries faced by the people of their era. Their works are considered as social commentary on the norms and tradition of the society. Khaled Hosseini a well-know Afghan-American writer, often talks about the terrible situation in Afghanistan in his book. During the soviet era, his family had to seek political asylum in the US, where he graduated in 1984. Hosseinigot his medical degree from the university of California,

San Diego's school of medicine in 1993. He is a doctor and now lives in America with his wife and two children. Khaled Hosseini, famous for his storytelling, still remembers the beauty of his home country. In his novels, he tries to address the common problems faced by people of Afghanistan. He is famous for his two best seller, "The kite Runner" and "A Thousand Splendid Suns". The novel covers themes like war, sadness, friendship, loyalty, hope, discrimination women's rights. More so, Hosseini does a good job showing how constant war affects Afghans' minds. In his first book, "The Kite Runner", he explores the emotions and thoughts of Amir, the man character, in his friendship with Hassan, who has both his friend and servant. Husseins novel shows how Afghan struggle with racial and cultural differences. In "The kite Runner", one character express a wish for Afghan for Pashtuns, Hosseini suggests that a big issue in Afghanistan is that different groups like Pushtuns, Tajiks, and Hazaras don't get along. In "A Thousand Splendid Suns" his concern seems to be a bit deviant, this time he points out the suffocation and harassment of women in Afghan society. Here he is quite successful to pull off the veil from the actual condition of women in Afghanistan. Also, Hosseini's novels set well sights on the socio-political condition of his homeland. In both of his novels Hosseini seems to be more concerned to present the war ridden era of Afghanistan and the effects of war on Afghans.

This novel mainly gyrates around the life of two Afghan women, Mariam and Laila. Mariam an illegitimate child of a well known person from Heart is forced to marry an aged man Rasheed. Laila on the other hand is the daughter of a university teacher; she is in love with her neighbor who left her for Pakistan because of growing tension of civil war in Kabul. Khaled Hosseini very artistically linked both Mariam and Laila together as Laila at the age of 15 also marries Rasheed after the death of her parents. Linking both Mariam and Liala gives artistic perfection to the work. For most of the critics, this novel only covers the theme of feminism and optimism however for many it also deals with the subject of history and the crumbling of Afghans among

themselves which is facilitating other nations to make them suffer. Hosseini very imaginatively narrates the story of Mariam and Laila in the crux of the Afghan civil war. It will not be wrong to call Khaled Hosseini as historian-cum-novelist. In simple term we can say that sub plots of both of his novels talk about the ground realities of Afghanistan. According to Hussein's the main cause of differences are the ethnical and racial superiority.

Objectives of the Research

1. To help the readers to approach this novel with a new angle in order to understand the socio- political conditions of Afghanistan.
2. It discusses the role of Afghan warlords and the machinations of external powers, their exploitation of poor masses which lead to the breakdown of Afghans as a nation.

Research Questions

1. What are the readers to approach this novel with a new angle in order to understand the socio- political conditions of Afghanistan?
2. What is the role of Afghan warlords and the machinations of external powers, their exploitation of poor masses which lead to the breakdown of Afghans as a nation?

Delimitation

Although the novel covers a number of themes, the researcher's study focused on the theme of disintegration in Afghans. It shows the major issues along with dialogues and the setting of the novel.

Significance of the Study

The research highlights the major social and political situation will help to understand the current socio/political situation of South-Asia, particularly in Afghanistan and Pakistan. It will also highlight the writer's political understanding of the settings in which he writes this particular piece of literature. It will also enable the students of literature to understand the relationship between literature and history that how literature of a nation can be linked with the history of that

nation. Beside that it will try to highlight the importance of unity amongst the different sects in a country.

Literature Review

Khaled Hosseini's "A Thousand Splendid Suns" talks about the issue of Afghanistan in a very attractive manner. His approach towards the historical event of Afghanistan is very unique in a way that he tries to relate those historical events in the life of his characters. Hosseini in a simple way tries to highlight the terrible history of Afghanistan in the form of a story. Hosseini wrote his first novel the "Kite Runner" with the same approach. It is autobiographical in its nature, Kite Runner highlights the miserable condition faced by the author and other Afghans in Afghanistan. The novel shows the unethical attitude of one cult towards another is creating miseries to the life of Afghans. For example Pashtuns in Afghanistan want to get rid of Tajik, Hazaras and so on. According to one of the character, "I'll ask the president to do what the king want to do, to free Afghanistan from all the dirty evils (Hosseini.36)". Two Solitudes, a Canadian novel also seems to be talking about the same issue of a rift between two different sects in Canada. Hugh Mac Lennan tried to explain the socio- political conditions of French Canadian and English Canadian. Since the rift between the two is mainly because of religion and economic variation, the novelist tried his level best to overcome the problem through mutual understanding. MacLennan appreciated both factions to overrule all these things and work for the prosperity of the country. Fighting on trivial issues is destroying Canada, is the main theme of MacLennan's, Two Solitudes. Like MacLennan's "Two Solitudes" "A Thousand Splendid Suns" also seems to be addressing the same issue. As Hosseini point out that "the main cause of Afghan miserable situation is the continuous civil wars between various groups. "A Thousand Splendid Suns" fights with each other over trivial issues. Both novels speak up against the curse of cultural, religious and social diversity in a country. The novelists explain that the only way to lead a country towards prosperity is harmony and

complete understanding between the people living in it. Both novels end with the note of hope and optimism. "To Kill a Mockingbird" by Hamper Lee also means to cover the curse of racial prejudice in the world. The novelist explains the sarcastic stance of white towards black, their humiliating approach and complete failure of the judicial system to protect the inferior ones. Alan Marshall in his article "The world through a mesh" published in The Telegraph(2007) pronounces that Hosseini's novel clearly illustrates the depiction of what was happening at that time in Afghanistan. According to him, the novel is "a view from inside the burqa of the nightmare of Afghanistan's history over 30 years" (Marshall,par.2). Moreover, the novel also deals with the changing perspective of Afghanistan, as it points out the conversion of Communism into gangsterism, reaching to the pits with the grim nihilism of the Taliban. For Alan Marshall "A Thousand Splendid Suns" should be termed as historical romance which tells the story of Afghanistan in a romantic way. Lisa See's "Mariam and Laila" published in The New York Times(2007) points out that after the success of Hosseini's first novel "The Kite Runner", his second novel "A Thousand Splendid Suns is an ambitious work" (See). Like the setting of his first novel, the setting of the second one is also Afghanistan however, this time he has taken the account of the last 33 years of chaotic history of war and subjugation but tried to present it through the life of two women. The war is enforced because of the personal enmity between the different sects living in the country. This makes a clear sense that Hosseini's basic purpose of the novel is to present the history of Afghanistan and to make the readers aware of what happened to Afghans in the last 30 years. Isabel Allende is quite right when she states that "the book is realistic as it highlights the real issues in Afghanistan. Furthermore, the tale of the novel makes the reader realize that they are roaming in the streets of war ridden Afghanistan. It looks like that everything is happening in front of them. Hosseini's novel present the actual situation of Afghanistan in front of us" (Allende).ErinHYPERLINK

"http://bestsellers.about.com/bio/Erin-Collazo-Miller-18778.htm"Collazo HYPERLINK "http://bestsellers.about.com/bio/Erin-Collazo-Miller-18778.htm" Miller admired Hosseini's novel as the greatest source of learning about Afghanistan. She presents both positive and negative aspects of the novel. The novel is a good source of the history understanding of the country. However, "Regime change, war, hope, and oppression are the drawbacks of the novel." Linta Wafdan Hidayah's research says that in the book "A Thousand Splendid Suns" by Khaled Hosseini, the family is frustrated and aggressive. She thinks when families are unhappy, it can make society unhappy too. This frustration and aggression can lead to violence, which is a sign of a society falling apart. So, she says, if a country is violent, it might mean it's not working well as a group. Robert I. Rotberg's book "When States Fail: Causes and Consequences" enlists few of the basic causes that leads the society towards disintegration. Internal violence, political instability and weak administrative government are the few basic reasons behind the disintegration of a nation. Rotberg seems to be very logical when he tries to hurl things related to the breakdown of a nation. For instance, Rotberg says that civil war is one of the main characteristics of a failed nation which mainly sprung because of some religious, ethnic and linguistic incongruity. (Rotberg) Beside that he also takes leadership as the contributing factor in the disintegration of a nation.

In Afghanistan warlords such as Gulbuddin Hakmatyar and Burrhan-ud-din Rabani worked for their own benefits which lead the country into civil war. Hosseini's novel explain the issue of the civil war in the best possible way. In the book, the characters often mention how Afghan leaders played a part in the starting the civil war. However , both Hosseini and Rotberg talk about the same concept of disintegration. Nationalism, according to Anthony Hyman, seems to be the weakest concept present among Afghans. The Afghans did not consider themselves as a nation; they seem to be proud of calling themselves as Pustuns, Tajiks, and Uzbek etc.He points out this aspect in his work "Nationalism in Afghanistan" and says that

except few educated people, rest of the individuals are indulged in the row that their ethnic class is superior to the rest present in the country. For example, for Pathan his race is superior as compared to the rest per say of races in the country. Rasheed the antagonist in the novel clearly explains this sort of mentality of Afghans. Being Pustun he considers himself superior to the rest of the clan. Hosseini's novel makes an effort to overrule this sort of things from Afghan society. Barnett R. Rubin in his book, "The Fragmentation of Afghanistan" very beautifully explains the situation in Afghanistan. He brings to the limelight the social and political conditions of Afghanistan. He discusses in detail the social construction of the Afghan society and the tribal system. He also gives in depth analysis of the changing condition of the Afghan society, especially after the coups of the communist party, after which the Afghan society was divided on ideological lines. He throws light on the Communist regimes in Afghanistan and their failures to rule successfully. Barnett R. Rubin also describes the role of Mujahedeen in changing the social and political situation of Afghanistan. Rubin, very skillfully describes the changing situations that finally lead to the establishment of complete chaos in Afghan society.

"The Search for Peace in Afghanistan: From Buffer State to Failed State" is another book by Barnett R. Rubin that deals with the crucial situation in Afghanistan. He explains that how after the coming of the Communists to power in Afghanistan, the buffer state of Afghanistan was turned into a failed state and then the whole country was plunged into an internal ethnic and religious struggle that in turn gave way to the interference of the foreign and regional powers in Afghanistan. He is of the view that the emergence of Taliban in Afghanistan was a solution for the failed state but unfortunately they could also not bring peace to the country and finally they faced destruction. A Thousand Splendid Suns also seems to be explaining the same things in lighter tones. Khaled Hosseini tries to explain the psychological effect of never ending war. Rubin tried to point out the cause of the war while Hosseini in his novel tried to present the effect of

the war. Hosseini explains all these things in the best possible way to his readers.

Rasul Bakhsh Rais's book Afghanistan: War without Winners, marvelously explains the struggle for power among Afghans warlords. He points out Afghan war as an unending game. In this book, the author also mentions the role of various ethnic leaders, regional powers and international actors. Beside that it also talks about the ending series war imposed upon Afghans from the last few centuries. Hosseini novel also point out these things as it says the country had invaded by many groups in several decades. Another important book about Afghanistan is, Afghanistan: The Soviet Invasion in Perspective, of Anthony Arnold. In this book the author tries to trace and assess the Soviet invasion of Afghanistan. He enumerates the history of the country from the times of Amir Abd-ur-Rehman Khan to the Soviet invasion and also elaborates the role played by the resistance forces and their outside supporters. The author brings to the lime light the interests of the Soviet Union in Afghanistan. The work of Jagmohan Meher under the title of "America's Afghanistan War: the Success that Failed", deals with the US role in Afghanistan since the times of the Soviet occupation. This work also focuses the role played by Pakistan and other outside actors in Afghanistan. Hosseini also empathizes on the role of Afghanistan's neighboring countries in the instability of Afghanistan as at one stage he says, "Pakistani and Arab Islamist...These are the big players and Afghanistan is their playground. (Hosseini 274)"The novelist here is pointing towards Pakistan and Arabs. Jag mohan Mehar is very critical about Pakistan's role in Afghanistan. Hafizullah Emadi's work of "State, Revolution and Super Powers in Afghanistan" describes the state structure in Afghanistan. He discusses the coming of the revolution in Afghanistan and the rivalry between the two super powers namely, the US and the USSR. It also deals with the rising of the resistance against the Soviets and the PDPA regimes. The book highlights the role played by the various outside actors in Afghanistan during and after the Soviet occupation.

"Islam and Resistance in Afghanistan", an edited work of Olivier Roy explains the role of Islam in the Afghan society. It enumerates the role of the mujahideen against the Soviets and the PDPA regimes. It tells that how Islam was brought to the forefront for presenting a formidable resistance. During the regime of Taliban citizens of Afghanistan has to follow Islam in the real sense. Hosseini also shows up this issue very artistically Islam, according to him, is not something to be imposed. Taliban makes the life of Afghans miserable. In long and short, Hosseini tried to present the true face and mental approach of Taliban and their way to govern. For them women are superior to men. "The Struggle for Afghanistan" by Nancy Peabody Newell and Richard S. Newell Mainly deals with the Soviet occupation of Afghanistan and the resistance forces during the initial years of the invasion. Since the novel begins in 1960s, Hosseini cracked through his novel to explain the situation of Afghanistan during these 40 years i.e. 1960 till 2000. The combined work of Syed Shabbir Hussain, Abdul Hamid Alvi and Absar Hussain Rizvi under the title of "Afghanistan under the Soviet Occupation" also describes the Soviet Invasion and occupation of Afghanistan and the Afghan nationalist resistance to them. This work also points out the impact of Soviet occupation of Afghanistan.

Research Methodology

The method of our research is qualitative and it focuses on giving a deep and detailed understanding of a topic. Tanjit Khumar says that this type of research is not limited by fixed rules, allowing the researchers to fully engage and uncover the deeper meaning behind issues. It involves analyzing data in a way that is often subjective and based on interpretation. The researcher has collected data from various dialogues and its source is "A Thousand Splendid Suns"

Theoretical Frame Work

Edward Goldsmith in his book "Can British Survive?" speaks about the causes and effects of social disintegration. According to him When

social systems or any other systems combine and form a larger one, they are said to be integrated, but When the opposite occurs, the larger system must be regarded as disintegrated – in other words, its order is being reduced; the bonds holding it together are being fragile until they cannot retain it no longer. At this point it breaks up into smaller systems. Goldsmith in his approach says that integration can happen at all levels of the organization. Afghanistan (the land of the Afghans) has a history of the strong tribal system. It has been subjected to foreign invasions for a long time. Strong bureaucracy, centralized government and strong administrative setup have been lacking in this landlocked country ever since. Tribal system has strong roots in the administrative setup of the society.

Such societies always face the problem of disintegration as there are no strong regulation and centralized government. In multiple power structures, there is always struggle within the tribes, which is aided by external influence as well. This power struggle continues to gain more space. The economy is another important factor and directly related to it poverty. It is a major contributor to disintegration as per the theory proposed by Goldsmith.

As stated by Goldsmith, we can enlist few major causes of disintegration in a nation.

Lack of proper administrative system

External influence i.e. Proletariats

Autocracy

Economic condition

Lack of educational system for both male and female

One can easily interpret the root cause of disintegration in Afghans in the light of the above mentioned points by Goldsmith. Furthermore we can also relate all these points to the situation presented by Khaled Hosseini in the work. According to Goldsmith the primitive function of a government is to hold the nation together. In fact it is the binding force between the disintegrated clans. However, in countries like Afghanistan where the system of government is totally under the control of culture, tradition and nepotism it is quite difficult for the system to prevail and perform its function properly.

Goldsmith in this article gives the reference from the book "Primitive Government" of Lucy Mair. He spots out this as:

The function of government is assumed by the citizens as a whole. The most important influence is tradition, any deviation from which is severely frowned upon. The ancestral spirits, the council of elders and public opinion in general combine to oppose and chastise any unnecessary departure from the traditions and customary law that is handed down from generation to generation (Goldsmith). Jirga system in the tribal belt of Pakistan and Afghanistan is the best example in this regard. Even the democratic government of Afghanistan established in 2004, is under the strong influence of the Afghan Loya Jirga. Thus according to Goldsmith it is quite difficult for democracy to prevail in such society and the ultimate result will be the destruction of the society. Proletariats or external influence is another contributing reason of social disintegration. By this Goldsmith actually means the settlement or involvement of external forces in a society in order to take advantage of the resources of a country. A proletariat, according to Goldsmith tends to develop once a country becomes prosperous. To explain his point of view he presents the example of Roman Empire which fell because of the strong influence of the proletariats settled in Roman Empire. Afghanistan, a country of great resources is always under the gaze of those Proletariats. Even in the novel we came across a number of dialogues which highlight the influence of external forces i.e. Pakistan, Arabs etc. Autocracy is another prominent feature which leads a society towards disintegration. The curse of a government by a single authority is explained by Goldsmith as "Destroys the spirit of self-reliance, the sense of duty to the community, all the associated cultural traits that together permit social self regulation (Goldsmith)".

For a long period, Afghanistan was ruled by Autocrats which has taken their society to the verge of disintegration and civil war. Economic condition is another contributory factor in the disintegration of a society. Poverty leads the society towards fragmentations. A nuclear family,

as reported by Goldsmith is not able to survive in harsh economic conditions. Afghanistan during late 1980's was unable to provide their citizens with the basic necessities of life thus resulting in the chaos. Lack of education especially of women, the violation of women's rights and cultural differences, all these are true and applicable to the Afghanistan problem. These are some of the major causes which have led to the disintegration of Afghans as a nation.

Results and Interpretations

A Thousand Splendid Suns unambiguously speaks of Hosseini's love for Afghanistan and its culture. From the very outset of the novel, we are presented with a number of historical entities related to Afghanistan. This chapter will focus on the concept of nationalism in Afghans and various causes of disintegration as described by Khaled Hosseini in the novel through various dialogues and setting. Moreover, it will analyze the data collated in the light of Goldsmith's theory of social disintegration. Disintegration, as portrayed in the novel, is both social and political. The causes of disintegration are manifold and are depicted through various narrative elements. Hosseini presents the reader with a society that is fractured by war, gender inequality, and cultural conflicts. The constant state of violence and unrest has a profound effect on the characters, eroding their sense of security and unity. This **social disintegration** is further exacerbated by the oppressive structures imposed by the Taliban, which suppress individual freedoms and deepen the existing divisions within society.

Lack of Administrative Setup

Humans are social by birth. For most of the philosophers, man is a social animal who is completely dependent upon others living in his surroundings. A human being living in complete isolation is either an animal or some mystic. From the very outset of this universe, humans are observed living in a very organized and peaceful manner. The need of authority to make them live in accordance with law is the sole motive of an organized society. Society without authority cannot be termed as legally organized. The Greeks

were the first to highlight the importance of the administrative setup in the smooth running of the state. They introduced the term "Politics" to explain the affairs of their cities. Aristotle was the first to relate individual with state. "Man" according to Aristotle "is by nature a political animal". By this he means to say that man is by birth political in his approach, every act of him comes under the loom of politics. However, the modern - day concept of Politics is totally opposite to the one explained above. The modern political scientist takes politics as a source of power. To run the affairs of the state one needs to have a proper system of government. Individual liberty is totally dependent upon the system of government working in the state. The term Government is usually defined as the "body that has power in a given unit-whether national, regional or local- and the whole constitutional system"(Robertson.142). There are different types of government such as democracy, autocracy, dictatorship etc. so in long and short; we can say that government is actually the machinery through which the affairs of the states are controlled. Executive, judiciary and legislative as per described by political pundit, are the three main components of government. Failure of any one of these three will lead a country or state towards complete chaos and anarchy. Khaled Hosseini in his novel "A Thousand Splendid Suns" aims to depict the grave effects of changing government on the lives of common Afghans. Furthermore, continuous regime change and lack of administrative setup is the root cause behind their plight. The story of "A Thousand Splendid Suns" begins during the regime of King Zahir Shah. The novel instigates with the beauties of Afghanistan. Afghans are presented as a proud nation. Their love for Afghan culture, art and tradition, according to Hosseini is beyond any limit. Jalil Khan, father of Mariam, in the beginning of the novel seems to be very enthusiastic and passionate about the past glories of Afghanistan. As he describes the city of Herat as "Herat,... had once been the cradle of Persian culture, the home of writers, painters, and Sufis" (Hosseini 4). King Zahir Shah ruled Afghanistan for forty years. Political stability was there and the administrative setup of the

government was running smoothly. Although King Zahir Shah was a monarch and liberal Afghans were strongly against his wretched form of government, yet he was able to deliver and provide ordinary Afghans with all sorts of basic necessities and up to some extent ordinary Afghans like Jalil Khan were in high spirits during his regime. But according to Hosseini in the summer of 1973 things start to change for the Afghan nation (21). The King was overthrown by his cousin Daoud Khan in a bloodless coup, which escorts the nation toward disintegration, few were happy with him while many cursed him for his brutal act. Although initially many Afghans were relieved with the change and accepted Daoud Khan as the democratic leader of Afghanistan, as Jalil Khan says that "Afghanistan is no longer a monarchy, Mariam. You see, it's a republic now, and Daoud Khan is the president" (Hosseini 22). Daoud Khan ruled Afghans for five long years in which he brought many social and political changes. Mainly known for his socialistic nature, Daoud Khan is dethroned in 1978 as a result of rising conflict between socialist and communist in Afghanistan. After the failure of monarchy and republic, Khaled Hosseini is going to introduce a new political term in his novel i.e. communism. He also makes it clear that in Afghanistan, ordinary people were not that much concerned with the political philosophy of Communism or Socialism. "What's a Communist?" (Hosseini 89). Is the question asked by most of the Afghans, With the defeat of Daoud Khan, Kabul witnessed a new form of administrative setup. The rebel force of Communist army, according to Hosseini declares that "our watan will now be known as the Democratic Republic of Afghanistan" (92). Furthermore, for the supporters of communism, "A new Afghanistan is born" (Hosseini 92) and Najibullah is appointed to rule over this new Afghanistan So from Zahir's monarchy into Daoud's Republic, the Afghan land now tastes new form of government i.e. Najibullah's Communistic version of Democracy. Like every new thing, communism also attracts Afghans and they start appreciating this mode of government. As at one point Hosseini very beautifully explains

the simple understanding of communism by Afghan nation "Maybe not so bad for us" (92). So for them the new system of administration imposed upon them will be based upon social equality and justice. Disintegration amongst Afghans becomes quite visible when some of the Afghans go in favor of Communism while many others start a war against the soviets. Shanzai, Laila's School teacher was a diehard fan of the Soviet Union, most of the time she used to say that "Soviet Union was the best nation in the world, along with Afghanistan" (Hosseini 101). Moreover she used to romanticize, soviet occupation of Afghanistan in a very astonishing way as she talks "that's why the soviet union came here in 1979. They wanted to help us fight against these mean people..." (Hosseini 101). For her the takeover of the Soviet Union over Afghanistan is actually "an Inqilab (Hosseini 102)". Soviets as per described by Shanzia is in Afghanistan, to make Afghans prosperous while on the other side of the picture there are a number of people who show a strong sense of detest for the Russians. Both Ahmed and Noor, brothers of Laila, are fighting against Soviet and want to drag them out of the country. Like them, youths from every sect were joining Mujahedeen against the Soviet forces. During the Communist regime Afghanistan witnessed the most unstable sort of governments. The instability can be understood more easily if we look at the number of heads of the state changed during a short span of time between 1978 till 1986. Najibullah, the last communist president of Afghanistan ruled Afghans with an iron fist. No one is allowed to raise their voice against his tyrannical mode of government. Amongst Afghans, Najibullah is known as "soviets' puppet president" (Hosseini 138). However, the decision of the Soviet Union to leave Afghanistan in 1988 bought a ray of hope for the inhabitants to live freely. With the exit of the Soviet Army from Kabul, people were dancing on air in the streets of Kabul. Eventually, the surrender of Najibullah in 1992, gives an ultimate end to the jihad of mujahedeen against the Soviet Union. As Khaled Hosseini explains that "The jihad is over...Mammy's heroes, Ahmad's and Noor's brother-in-war, had won" (Hosseini 144). Now the

administrative setup is in the hand of Mujahedeen, who took over Kabul. Thus, now the streets of Kabul witness the roar of their new master i.e. The Mujahedeens. Mujahedeen were actually small groups of fighter who fought against the Soviet Union. Each bit of a fighter is governed by a known person. Khaled Hosseini gives a brief account of these groups elaborating the vast ethnic diversity in Afghanistan. The Mujahedeen, According to Khaled Hosseini, mainly comprise of: There were different leaders during the war. Dostum was one, known for changing sides. Then, there was Hekmatyar, a Pashtun who studied engineering and once killed a student. Rabbani taught Islam at Kabul University. Sayyaf was a stout Muslim with Arab ties. Mazari, also known as Baba Mazari, had strong ties to Iran. Beside that Ahmad Shah Massoud, a Tajik by origin is widely known and most appreciated leader of Mujahedeen. Since all these groups of Mujahedeen belong to different sect and ethnic background. It was hard for them to unite and accept the leadership of anyone amongst themselves. Thus it was decided between the groups, that the Leadership Council will be formed which will choose the President of Afghanistan. After consulting each and every leader of the groups, the council "elected Rabbani president" (Hosseini 154) which gave birth to sever crises. Some fractions of Mujahedeen objected the selection of Rabbani as president, while other stand for Rabbani. The tussle begins as the Mujahedeen start accusing each other's, now disintegration become dominant amongst them. Now their enemy is not a monarch, nor communist but their own self. "The Mujahedeen, armed to the teeth but now lacking a common enemy, had found the enemy in each other" (Hosseini 155). The situation is now clear and shows that complete chaos took over Afghanistan; the country is now completely encrypted into the curse of civil war. Not even Mujahedeen, people at ordinary level start brawling with each other and begin to call each other's traitors and turncoats. Like Afghanistan, Kabul city is now divided into bits and parts. No person from the other sect is allowed to enter into the area of their opponents.

This chaotic situation has a psychological effect on the mind of Afghans. Now they become used to, as the novelists say "old war had ended and new ones had broken out" (Hosseini 229), but now things went unnoticed. They are now completely fed up with bloodshed in their country. In *A Thousand Splendid Suns*, Khaled Hosseini paints a vivid picture of Afghanistan's tumultuous history and the devastating impact of conflict on its people. The novel traces decades of war, beginning with the Soviet invasion, moving through the rise of the Mujahideen, the civil war, and the eventual rule of the Taliban. In particular, the city of Kabul, once known for its rich cultural heritage, is depicted as a city torn apart by years of violence. The inhabitants of Kabul, much like the characters in the novel, are forced to adapt to a reality where their city is divided, not just physically by destruction, but also socially and politically. The constant power struggles between different factions have left deep scars on the city's population. People become prisoners in their own neighborhoods, unable to cross into areas controlled by rival sects or factions, which fuels further distrust and isolation among the communities. Hosseini highlights how this continuous cycle of violence takes a profound psychological toll on the Afghan people. Characters like Mariam and Laila symbolize the emotional and mental resilience required to survive in such a fractured world. Yet, they, like many Afghans, are also worn down by the endless bloodshed. The once-inconceivable horrors of war become routine, and people develop a kind of emotional numbness to survive. The quote, "old war had ended and new ones had broken out," reflects the tragic reality that many Afghans experience—where even when one conflict subsides, another inevitably takes its place. The constant presence of violence and instability fosters a sense of hopelessness, as people become desensitized to the chaos around them. The novel portrays the exhaustion and disillusionment of a nation that has seen too much war, with many characters expressing a deep yearning for peace, even as they continue to live in a world where peace seems increasingly elusive. The sense of being "fed up" with the violence is not just an

emotional state but a collective psychological burden carried by generations of Afghans who have known nothing but conflict.

On September 1996, new invaders, The Taliban's, attacked Kabul. Continuous fighting between the sects of Mujahedeen paved the way for Taliban's to launch attacks and have defeated many Warlords in different provinces. The best thing about Taliban's, according to Hosseini is that they are united under one leadership. With their arrival in Kabul, a new form of government is now imposed upon the wrecked nation of Afghanistan, the Islamic mode of government. From the very beginning of their era, dead set of rules was announced and it is made clear that violation of the law is intolerable. Declaring that "Our country is known as the Islamic Emirate of Afghanistan"(Hosseini 247). Taliban makes it clear that the Land will allow only the law of Quran and Sunnah. Khaled Hosseini severely opposed Taliban and objected their mode of government which is a totally Islamic version of government. They enforce women to stay at home and banned education for them. The Taliban mode of government gave Afghans nothing but hate and harshness. Though the grave purpose of their government is to impose Sharia, however no attention is lent towards the basic rights of humans. Khaled Hosseini seems to be justified when he pointed out Taliban's regime as the complete destruction of Afghanistan. What we have observed so far, lack of stable and efficient governmental setup is the root cause of disintegration of Afghans. They fought against each other because no one is there to guide and lead them properly. Since the regime of King Zahir Shah till Taliban's, every time a new set of rules is imposed to administrate the Afghans. The primary function of good administrative government is to hold and bind the nation into a chain of brotherhood. But in Afghanistan, from Zahir Shah to Daoud Khan, from Daoud Khan to Najibullah, and from Najibullah to Mullah Umer, nobody ever tried to unite the disintegrated clans of Afghans.

Beside lack of administration, unequal distribution of power between the sects is also a prominent factor of detest amongst Afghans.

Hosseini explained this well through the words of Hakim. As he says that "But when one group rules over the others for so long . .

. There's contempt. Rivalry. There is. There always has been." (Hosseini 117). The Pustuns hold the premier post in Afghanistan for a long period of time which gave birth to the rivalry and jealousy between them. Thus the unjust distribution of power among the sect is the vital force before the splitting of the Afghan nation. A leader is selected not because of his abilities but because of his ethnic background.

External Influence

The role played by external forces is very vital and worth mentioning in the disintegration or splitting of nations. Histories of the nations made it quite clear that behind every partition of a nation, there is some external hand involved. Separation of East and West Pakistan is the best example in this regard. India played a vital role in the disintegration of Pakistan in 1971. Exploitation of East Pakistan, now Bangladesh, allowed India to curb West Pakistan. So we can say that internal clashes allow the external exploiter to get whatever they want from the weaker nation. However, the internal conflict between the sects is more crucial as compared to the external influence. According to experts, external influence on a nation is only possible when there is some internal conflict between different groups. No nation can exploit or draw advantage of a united and integrated society or nation. Afghanistan, because of its geographical importance and the resources it has, always remained an eye catcher for super as well as for the regional powers. Khaled Hosseini explains the importance of Afghanistan for external world in a very alarming way. From historical evidences it is clear that Afghanistan from ages remained a center of focus for the rulers of the world. Continuous external influence is explained by the novelist as Kaled Hosseini explains the distressing history of Afghanistan as "And that, . is the story of our country, one invader after another," the driver said, flicking cigarette ash out the window. "Macedonians, Sassanians, and Arabs. Mongols. Now the Soviets.(132) In *A Thousand Splendid*

Suns, Khaled Hosseini shows how Afghanistan has been the center of attention for many powerful rulers and empires throughout history. The country's location at the crossroads of different regions has made it a valuable target for invaders, causing constant foreign interference. Hosseini highlights this point in a conversation between characters, where a driver reflects on Afghanistan's long history of being invaded: "And that,... is the story of our country, one invader after another. Macedonians. Sassanians. Arabs. Mongols. Now the Soviets" (132). This line speaks to the fact that Afghanistan has been invaded over and over again by various empires, from ancient times to the modern era. The Macedonians, led by Alexander the Great, invaded the region in the 4th century BCE, followed by the Sassanians, an ancient Persian empire. Later, the Arabs came in the 7th century, bringing Islam, and in the 13th century, the Mongols, led by Genghis Khan, swept through, leaving a path of destruction. In the 20th century, the Soviets invaded, once again pulling Afghanistan into conflict. Hosseini uses these historical events to show how the Afghan people have suffered from this endless cycle of invasions. The country's rich culture and history have often been overshadowed by the violence and instability brought by foreign powers. Afghanistan's strategic location, between powerful regions like Central Asia, the Middle East, and South Asia, made it a key area for empires to control. However, this has also meant that the Afghan people have had to endure repeated wars and destruction. Each new invader brought new challenges, forcing the people to adapt, fight, and survive in the face of constant turmoil. The characters in *A Thousand Splendid Suns* live through modern examples of this foreign interference. They experience the Soviet invasion, which leads to a brutal war in the 1980s. This war leaves deep scars on Afghanistan and its people. After the Soviets leave, the country does not find peace. Instead, it becomes a battleground for different groups fighting for power, leading to a civil war. Then the Taliban rise to power, bringing a new kind of suffering and oppression. Hosseini's characters are caught in this cycle, living through one conflict after

another, with foreign powers always playing a role in the country's fate.

Hosseini's portrayal of Afghanistan's history serves as a warning. He shows how the continuous interference from external forces has had a lasting impact on the Afghan people, creating a cycle of violence that is difficult to escape. Afghanistan's struggles are not just a product of internal issues but are also the result of constant pressure and manipulation by foreign powers. In the novel, this theme becomes clear through the experiences of the characters, who are left to deal with the consequences of decisions made by distant rulers and invaders. Through this, Hosseini emphasizes the importance of understanding Afghanistan's history and the heavy price its people have paid for their country's strategic importance to the rest of the world. Nations after nations attacked Afghanistan but nobody was able to conquer or rule over this piece of land. Every invader had to face resistance from the loyal and brave Afghans. The pages of the novel narrate the tale of Afghanistan starting from 1970's till 2004. During these three decades, Afghanistan faces harsh and critical situation. Trespassers and exploiters tried their level best to occupy the land but none of them achieve their targets. The Afghans face harsh situation mainly because, the trespassers were able to disintegrate them. They were able to divide them socially, politically and religiously. However, still they managed to survive in those callous circumstances. The Russian, in 1970's was able to enter Afghanistan under the shade of communism. They use political phenomena of Communism to take over Afghanistan. The Afghans were divided on political grounds. Some favor communism, some oppose it, few termed it un-Islamic to be Communist. In broader perspective, Afghanistan actually serves the battlefield in the war between Communism and Capitalism. The Russian Communist faces the Capitalist American in the territory of Afghanistan. The war is between two super-powers while the consequence is faced by Poor Afghanistan. Hosseini recites all this, very masterly as he hints that " the president of the united state Reagan, had given weapon and training to

Mujahideen counter down Soviet union" (Hosseini 102).

The above mentioned lines make it clear that, land of the Afghans has been exploited to overcome the rising Communism in the world. The leviathan of communism is being trapped by the monster of Capitalism in Afghanistan. The external influence of Russians, Americans and Muslim world have extremely damaged Afghanistan both internally and externally. Continuous internal war in the country has also psychologically effected Afghans. The family system is badly affected by the long plight of war. Like Russia and America, both Pakistan and Saudi Arabia, also played an influential role in Afghanistan. Pakistan being the next door neighboring country interfere more as compared to the rest of the country. Expulsion of Soviet Union was possible because of Pakistan's extended support to the Mujahideen. Pakistani religious, political and military personnel show their deep concern in the internal matters of Afghanistan. It is worldwide accepted that, Talibans in Afghanistan are fully supported by Pakistan. Hosseini explained the role of Pakistan and Arab countries as at one stage one of the characters says that "Meet our real masters,...Pakistani and Arab Islamists"(Hosseini 274).

In *A Thousand Splendid Suns*, Khaled Hosseini touches on the significant role Pakistan and Arab countries played in Afghanistan's internal conflicts, particularly during the Soviet occupation and the rise of the Taliban. The expulsion of the Soviet Union in the 1980s was heavily influenced by Pakistan's extended support to the Mujahideen, Afghan fighters who resisted the Soviet invasion. Pakistan, along with the backing of Arab nations, provided arms, training, and logistical support to these fighters. This support wasn't limited to just military aid but also included religious and political influence, as Pakistan's religious leaders and military personnel became deeply involved in Afghanistan's internal affairs.

Hosseini captures this reality through the voice of one of his characters who remarks, "Meet our real masters,... Pakistani and Arab Islamists" (Hosseini 274). This statement reflects how, over time,

Afghanistan's independence was undermined by the influence of external forces, particularly from neighboring Pakistan and wealthy Arab countries. While the Soviet Union was eventually forced to withdraw from Afghanistan in 1989, the involvement of these external powers did not end there. Instead, their influence continued to shape the future of the country, especially with the rise of the Taliban in the 1990s. It is widely acknowledged that Pakistan provided significant support to the Taliban as they rose to power, with both financial and military aid coming from Pakistani sources. Pakistan's intelligence agency, the ISI, played a key role in arming and organizing the Taliban, helping them seize control of large parts of Afghanistan. Arab countries, particularly Saudi Arabia, also contributed by funding religious schools, or madrassas, where many of the Taliban leaders were educated. These schools promoted a hardline interpretation of Islam, which later became the ideological foundation of the Taliban movement.

Hosseini's portrayal of Pakistan and Arab involvement highlights how Afghanistan's fate was heavily influenced by its neighbors, who often acted in their own interests rather than considering the needs and well-being of the Afghan people. Pakistan's involvement was driven by its desire to maintain influence in Afghanistan and counter Indian influence in the region. Meanwhile, Arab countries supported the Taliban and other Islamist groups as part of a broader effort to promote their religious and political ideologies. Through his narrative, Hosseini suggests that Afghanistan became a battleground for competing interests, not only from global superpowers like the Soviet Union and the United States but also from regional players like Pakistan and Arab states. This external meddling contributed to the ongoing instability and conflict in the country, as various factions vied for power with the backing of foreign sponsors. The characters in *A Thousand Splendid Suns* are caught in the middle of this geopolitical struggle, their lives deeply affected by decisions made far beyond Afghanistan's borders. According to Hossein the Taliban and the Afghans Warlords are plaything in the hands of external forces. They are using

them for their own purposes. Pakistan motivated Taliban to use extreme force in Afghanistan to extract maximum benefit out of the situation. In other words, Pakistan support Taliban which are mainly Pushtuns in origin, thus appreciating one particular sect to work against the rests. Moreover, the Taliban was also supported by U.S.A against Soviet Union. They exploit them till the end and when their purpose is achieved. They left them unnoticed. Once they grow powerful enough it becomes quite difficult for the world to control the Taliban. Ahmad Shah Massoud is well aware of the fact that, the Taliban is not only threat to Afghanistan but for the whole world so everybody should play their role to end the tyrannical rule of the Taliban. Edwardes Goldsmith used the term "Proletariats" to explain the concept of external influence on a country. Afghanistan, according to Hosseini, remained a focal point for the proletariats from all parts of the worlds. The basic purpose of these proletariats is to ship out the resources of the country. Furthermore, these proletariats took all the sects towards disintegration. The Pushtuns were favored by Pakistan and Saudi Arabia. Europeans were supporting Tajiks while several other minority groups are also honored by many other proletariats. While big fishes like American and Russian, exploits different Afghan groups according to their own need.

Economic Conditions

Another prominent factor of disintegration amongst nation is its economic conditions. Economically weak societies tend to disintegrate more easily as compared to the one which stable. Generally it is presumed that an economically stable society is one in which there is constant political stability so that the foreign Investment tend to pours in the economy of the state, GDP rate is getting higher day by day and the literacy rate of the nation is up to the mark. These are some of the salient features of an economic stable society.

In the pages of a novel, Hosseini tried to present the Afghan society economically divided into two parts i.e. the Rich and the Poor Afghans. The rich are presented as mere exploiter of the poor. Jalil

Khan, for instance exploits poor Nana, trapped her in love and then left her to spend her life in the Premises of Kolba. Nana well aware of the nature of rich proclaims that "Rich man telling rich lies" (Hosseini 5). As the story proceeds, Hosseini instantly presents a sharp distinction between rich and poor living in Kabul. At one side of the city only rich used to live, as described by the novelist as "This is where rich people, diplomats, and royal family members live, not like us." (Hosseini 66). Clearly indicates that this part of the city only belongs to the rich and no poor is allowed in this part. The distinction becomes more vivid as Khaled Hosseini point out that "The women in this part of Kabul were a different breed from the women in the poorer neighborhoods" (Hosseini 67). Thus people living in this portion of Kabul are almost different from the ones spending time in the neighborhood showing a strong sense of separation. People, living in the rich localities of Kabul are termed as more modern and liberal as compared to the one living in surrounding of Deh-Mazang who considers the rich and liberals as "targeting their own self respect and their honor and pride" (Hosseini 63). Through the economic conditions of individuals Khaled Hosseini, has shown very beautifully the mentality of individuals. The economically dominant males are shown to be more liberal as compared to the one which have less chance to earn bread and butter. During the regime of Taliban, very few opportunities for Economic growth were offered which not only split up the society but forced the families to split. For example, due to economic depression, Laila is forced to admit Aziza in an orphanage.

Furthermore, splitting of society seems to be very visible when we take the account of economic conditions. The rich is not allowing the poor to have a close acquaintance with them, while the poor consider the rich as honor and pride less. Education is another visible factor in the novel which divides the society. Generally in societies like Pakistan and Afghanistan, women are not allowed to get education which gives rise to a number of problems. Economic instability is the one of them. In the modern states role of women is very much important. Men alone can't generate

enough, a women's cooperation can be a source of relief for him. Hosseini appreciates women to contribute in the development of the country. According to him "Marriage can wait, education cannot" (Hosseini 105). So a woman should prefer education over marriage. Her first priority should be education rest of the thing would be done later on. The writer believes that men and women both contribute to a country's development. He says, "When this war is over, Afghanistan will need you as much as its men, maybe even more" (Hosseini 103). This shows that women will be important in the country's progress. Not only men, women can also play their role in the development of the nation. An educated woman can add a lot more to the economy of a nation.

In the beginning of Taliban government, the first instruction approved by them was to prohibit women to get education as it was announced by them that "Girls are forbidden from attending school. All schools for girls will be closed immediately. Women are forbidden from working" (Hosseini 249). In this regard the era Taliban ruled over Afghanistan can be termed as black era. Without progressing, Afghan society faces a number of new challenges. Lack of education, and critical economic condition were mainly behind the suppression of Afghan society. No one dared to raise his voice against the barbaric regime of the Taliban. The time when the Taliban ruled Afghanistan is often seen as a dark period in the country's history. During this era, many new problems arose for Afghan society, especially due to strict rules like banning girls from going to school and preventing women from working. This lack of education and poor economic conditions greatly contributed to the suppression of Afghan society. People lived in fear, as no one was brave enough to stand up against the harsh and cruel rule of the Taliban. As a result, Afghanistan was unable to progress and improve its situation during that time.

Findings and Conclusions

Summary

A Thousand Splendid Suns like any source of history take its reader to the premises of Afghanistan and provide comprehensive

information of Afghans living. The goal is to discuss the past, present, and future of the land. No other writer has described the land as vividly as Khaled Hosseini. Among many themes, the researcher aimed to explore how and why the Afghan people are different in the novel. The researcher chooses certain dialogues and settings to support his point. Following are the findings after the analysis of data collected from the course of the novel.

Findings

Basically this research is conducted in order to look at how Khaled Hosseini has utilized his storytelling technique to present what are the root causes of Afghan's agonies. After reading his second novel, *A Thousand Splendid Suns*, the researcher found out that one of the major causes of Afghanistan is its disintegrated people. Certain dialogues and setting in the novel have been selected and analyzed thoroughly to understand the theme of disintegration in Afghans. Although, apparently the novel intends to highlight the miserable life of Afghan women in the backdrop of war; after thorough analysis of the data the researcher is now able claim that not only women but men as well as the whole Afghan community is shown miserable and trapped by Hosseini in the novel. They have been shown pinched and disintegrated, not willing to console each other in the high time of tension. Khaled Hosseini makes his approach through the course of the novel that if a nation wants to have a prestigious status in the world, then the basic requirement for them is to be united; no nation can survive until and unless they are united. A divided and alienated nation can never raise their voice against the suppressors. As the individuals of the nation start standing for each other's rights, the nation starts progressing. Not only Nations but divided individuals also suffer a lot. Mariam and Laila's struggle against Rasheed's brutal attitude is the best example in this regard. Initially both Mariam and Laila stay away from each other making it easier for Rasheed to deal with them. Mariam, usually avoids from Laila as she says to her that "I won't be your servant,"(Hosseini 2022). But once Laila her and tried to stop Rasheed from beating Mariam,

things start to change between the two. Now they start integrating against the evil acts of the society. The ultimate result of their unification helps them to have a serene life in chaotic surrounding. The analogy of Mariam and Laila is applicable to the disturbed situation of Afghanistan. Their disintegration allowed the Soviets, American, and Pakistanis to exploit them. Their war against each other provides others with an opportunity to deal them in an awful manner.

The data further reveal that the role of Afghan leadership is also very discouraging. None of Afghan warlords works to unite the disintegrated clans. In fact, for them tribalism seems to be more important than nationalism. From Zahir Shah till Taliban everybody has their own phenomena which they want to be imposed upon the poor masses of this region. Continuous change in the policies of the country is another major cause of Afghan's separateness.

Conclusion

In "*A Thousand Splendid Suns*" his concern seems to be a bit deviant, this time he points out the suffocation and harassment of women in Afghan society. Here he is quite successful to pull off the veil from the actual condition of women in Afghanistan. Also, Hosseini's novels set well sights on the socio-political condition of his homeland. In both of his novels Hosseini seems to be more concerned to present the war ridden era of Afghanistan and the effects of war on Afghans. This novel mainly gyrates around the life of two Afghan women, Mariam and Laila. Mariam an illegitimate child of a well-known person from Heart is forced to marry an aged man Rasheed. Laila on the other hand is the daughter of a university teacher; she is in love with her neighbor who left her for Pakistan because of growing tension of civil war in Kabul. Khaled Hosseini very artistically linked both Mariam and Laila together as Laila at the age of 15 also marries Rasheed after the death of her parents. Linking both Mariam and Laila gives artistic perfection to the work. For most of the critics, this novel only covers the theme of feminism and optimism however for many it also deals with the subject of history and the crumbling of Afghans among

themselves which is facilitating other nations to make them suffer. Hosseini very imaginatively narrates the story of Mariam and Laila in the crux of the Afghan civil war. It will not be wrong to call Khaled Hosseini as historian-cum-novelist. In simple term we can say that sub plots of both of his novels talk about the ground realities of Afghanistan. According to Hussein's the main cause of differences are the ethnical and racial superiority.

Recommendations

After complete analysis of various dialogues and the setting of the novel, the intellectual tried to bring the subject of separateness in a nation. The novel "A Thousand Splendid Suns ", according to the researcher, aims to talk about the social and political dilemma of Afghans. The study proposes certain recommendations and suggestions to understand the socio-political situation of Afghanistan and Pakistan. The researcher through the study tried to present the real problem faced by Afghans as a nation. Lack of competent leadership is one of the chief problems faced by Afghan throughout their history. None of their leader was able to solve the problems of the land; in fact none of them is sincere with Afghanistan. Almost all the leaders failed to administrate the system properly. Throughout the pages of the novel, it has been made clear that all the leaders of Afghanistan from Daoud Khan till Mulla Umer, were not the choice of ordinary Afghans. But they hold the highest office of the state as a result of some assault. In order to avoid such crumbling situation, the researcher recommends a proper mechanism i.e. the true spirit of Democracy should be imposed for the selection of the representative and leader of the state. The selection should be done through a free and fair system of election. Moreover the system of election should not only facilitate the major clan of the country but should allow people from minorities to have fair enough representation. Certain limitations should be imposed upon the representative of the people. They should be well-versed, educated and sincere. Besides that, the people of a nation should also hold their representative accountable for all his wrong doing.

A proper system of check and balance is appreciated in this regard. Only a competent authority is able to protect the nation from external subjugation.

Pakistan, neighboring country of Afghanistan shares a long list of cultural and intellectuals similarity with each other. Both countries face similar challenges and problems. Pakistan like Afghanistan is "the old sow that eats her farrow"(Joyce). Lack of competent leadership, ruin of governmental institution and continuous external influence are the major problems faced by Pakistan and these are quite similar to those faced by Afghanistan in the past. The study also aims to relate the problems of Pakistan with that of Afghanistan and gives an ultimate solution to the cope up with the situation. Afghanistan according to the study provides a didactic lesson for the peoples of Pakistan. Since Afghan has suffered a lot in the recent past, the text of the novel gives a moral lesson that if a want prestige than they should be united. Racial and religious prejudices like in Afghanistan will lead Pakistan towards complete chaos.

The study also recommends the importance of education for both male and females. According to the research, for a prosperous nation the basic chunk is literacy. An illiterate society can never make a country prosperous. Governmental setup is motivated to pay more and more attention on this issue.

References

- Arnold, Anthony. The Soviet Invasion in Perspective. New Delhi: Heinemann Publishers(Pvt.) Ltd, 1987.
- Biography. n.d. Web. 06 January 2012. <<http://www.khaledhosseini.com/hosseini-bio.html>>.
- Emadi, Hafiz Ullah. State, Revolution and Superpowers in Afghanistan. Karachi: Royal Book Company, 1997.
- Goldsmith, Edward. Can Britain Survive? London: Tom Stacey Ltd., 1971.

- Hidayah, LintaWafdan. Aggression in Domestic Violence Based on Frustration- Aggression Described in KhaledHosseini'sA Thousand Splendid Suns. Malang: Maulana Malik Ibrahim State Islamic University of Malang, 2009.
- Hosseini, Khaled. A Thousand Splendid Suns. London: Bloomsbury Publishing Plc, 2007.
- The Kite Runner. London: Bloomsbury Publishing Plc, 2007.
- Hussain, Syed Shabbir, Abdul Hamid Alvi, Absar Hussain Rizvi. Afghanistan under Soviet Occupation. Islamabad: World Affairs Publication, 1980.
- Hyman, Anthony. "Natiionalism in Afghanistan." International Journal of Middle East Studies (2002): 299-315.
- Lee, Harper. To Kill A Mockingbird. New York: Warner Books, Inc., 1960.
- Maclennan, Hugh. Two Solitudes. Newpress Canadian Classics, n.d.
- Marshall, Alan. The world through a mesh 31 May 2007.
- Meher, Jagmohan. America's Afghanistan War: The Success that Failed. Delhi :Kalpaz Publications, 2004.
- Nancy Peabody Newell, Richard S. Newell . The Struggle for Afghanistan .London : Cornell University Press, 1981.
- Pound, Ezra. ABC of Reading. New York: New Directions Publishing Corp, 2010. Rais, RasulBakhsh. War Without Winners. Karachi: Oxford University Press, 1994.
- Robertson, David. The Penguin Dictionary of Politics. London: Penguin Books, 1986.
- Rotberg, Robert I. When States Fail: Causes and Consequences. New Jersey: Princeton University Press, 2004.
- Roy, Olivier. Islam and Resistance in Afghansitan . New York: Cambridge University Press, 1990.
- Rubin, Barnett R. The Fragmentation of Afghanistan . London: Yale University Press, 2002.
- The Search for Peace in Afghanistan: From Buffer State to Failed State. London: Yale University Press, 1995.
- See, Lisa. "Sunday Book Review." Mariam and Laila 3 June 2007.

